

Biomimetic synthesis of monoterpene indole alkaloids from aglucones of secologanin derivatives : pH controlled product selectivity

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Variation of the pH for hydrolysis of secologanin derivatives with β -glucosidase controls rearrangement of the aglucone to afford different products, and hence stereoselective syntheses of heteroyohimbine, yohimbine and *Aspidosperma*-type alkaloids; with baker's yeast chemoselective reduction can also be achieved to give a precursor for antirrhine and related alkaloids.

The rich variety of functionality and skeleta among the thousands of indole alkaloids, combined with their pharmacological properties, has long intrigued and challenged generations of chemists, for both structure elucidation and synthesis. Eventually, all were found to have a common biogenetic origin from a single universal precursor, the glucoalkaloid strictosidine **3**, formed by condensation of tryptamine **2** with the monoterpene secologanin **1**¹. Our interest in glucoalkaloids began over thirty years ago, when collaboration with an Indian chemist, Professor L. R. Row, resulted in the isolation from *Adina cordifolia* and structure determination of the first secologanin derivative to be found in the indole alkaloid series, cordifoline **4**, which was also the first of the carboxy-alkaloids, derived from tryptophan². This unique discovery stimulated much work in the area and further fruitful collaboration with other Indian scientists, in particular Professor (Mrs.) A. Chatterjee and Dr. J. Banerji on structure elucidation of the cadambines from *Anthocephalus cadamba*, and Dr. R. S. Kapil³. When we found *Lonicera* species to be an excellent source of secologanin in large quantities, we started a programme of synthesis of indole and related alkaloids, in general using biogenetically patterned routes⁴.

Spengler condensation of tryptamine and secologanin to give strictosidine (and/or its C-3 epimer vincoside), followed by hydrolysis of the glucoside with subsequent rearrangement and reduction of the aglucone. We thus achieved considerable success in stereoselective syntheses of various secoyohimbine and heteroyohimbine alkaloids^{4a,b}. However, we considered that a more efficient approach might be to alter the sequence and carry out the Pictet-Spengler reaction as the last rather than the first step, which would obviate the use of an *N*-benzyl blocking group required for selective generation of a single C-3 epimer or the formation of C-3 epimeric mixtures in its absence. Our rationale was that cyclization of the indole onto a six-membered piperidine ring in a chair conformation would necessarily involve stereoelectronic control leading to one preferred C-3 configuration.

To this end we required a protecting group for the C-5 aldehyde of secologanin during the enzymatic hydrolysis and subsequent reduction steps. An acetal was intrinsically attractive since acid-catalyzed removal could in principle also promote Pictet-Spengler cyclization. After some experimentation with the dimethyl acetal, the more stable ethylene ac-

Heteroyohimbines⁵

Initially, we followed the *in vivo* sequence, i.e. Pictet-

etal group in **5** was found to be preferable. Thus acetylation of secologanin followed by ethylene glycol in presence of

characteristic fragments at m/z 184, 170, 169, 156, and by the loss of the NMR signal for the indolic H-2 in **9**. A complete analysis of its 400 MHz ^1H NMR spectrum in d_6 - Me_2CO established the structure as 3-isoajmalicine **11**. Thus H-20 (δ 2.05) had a small *cis ae* coupling of 3.5 Hz with H-19 (δ 4.48) and a *trans aa* coupling of 11.5 Hz with H-15 (δ 1.95), which in turn had a *trans aa* coupling of 12 Hz with H-14_{ax} (δ 1.59); with the last H-3 (δ 4.56) had a *cis ae* coupling of 5 Hz, so that the relative stereochemistry must be as in **11A**. Furthermore, the absolute configuration at C-3 was corroborated as *R* from a negative Cotton effect at 286 nm in the CD spectrum ($-4.7 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ dmol}^{-1}$)⁶.

As we had anticipated, exclusive generation of this stereochemistry in the Pictet-Spengler cyclization was attributable to kinetic axial attack by the indole at a C-3/N-4 iminium ion in an intermediate **10A** locked in a chair-like conformation by equatorial C-15 and 20 substituents. Finally, heating **11** in glacial acetic acid epimerized C-3 to the thermodynamically preferred *trans*-quinolizidine structure of (–)-ajmalicine **12**, m.p. 248–251°, characterised by a broadened doublet at δ 3.43 for H-3 with a *trans*-diaxial coupling of 12 Hz to H-14_{ax} in the NMR spectrum and a +ve Cotton effect at 280 nm in the CD spectrum, and identified by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Inversion of 3-isoajmalicine to ajmalicine was also achieved by lead tetra-acetate oxidation followed by sodium borohydride reduction.

Yohimbines^{7,8}

During the above enzymatic hydrolysis of secologanin derivatives, we found that it was crucial to maintain the pH at precisely 5.0 to optimize the yield of the dihydropyran aldehyde, and a significant discovery was that at pH 7.0 a different product predominated. Thus, after four days at 37° with β -glucosidase in pH 7.0 buffer, the ethylene acetal **5** afforded in 70% yield a cyclohexene aldehyde **14**, [α]_D+11.5° (CHCl_3), evidently formed in an alternative rearrangement via vinylogous aldol reaction of **13**, the dialdehyde tautomer of the ring-opened aglucone **6**. The ^1H NMR spectrum showed it to consist of essentially only one isomer with *trans-trans* C-7, 8, 9 stereochemistry. Hence the aldol cyclization had achieved virtually complete stereoselection with the single chiral centre at C-7 (*S*) inducing *R* chirality at both C-8 and C-9 in **14**, a result attributable to a chair-like transition state with all the 7, 8 and 9 substituents equatorial. Evidently we were in possession of a crucial precursor for synthesis of the yohimbine class of *Corynanthe* alkaloids, a target that had eluded us in the conventional bio. imetic route via strictosidine, by following a sequence (Scheme 2) analogous to that for the heteroyohimbines.

Subsequent reductive amination of the aldehyde with tryptamine proved problematic due to mixtures formed by competing conjugate reduction under a variety of conditions and reducing agents. However, eventually it was found that over-reduction could be essentially avoided by the use of sodium cyanoborohydride in methanol as for the heteroyohimbines above, to afford in *ca.* 85% yield the desired amine **15**. The structure was corroborated by the ^1H NMR spectrum with signals for both indole [δ 8.29 (s, HN-1), 7.7–7.1 (m, *arH*₄), 7.10 (bs, H-2)] and monoterpene [δ 5.59 (bd, H-19), 4.79 (t, H-3), 3.83 (s, CO_2Me)] moieties. Again, heating the crude product in a 1 : 1 acetone/10% aq. hydrochloric acid gave, in 75% yield on crystallisation from acetone, a single compound, m.p. 140–142°, [α]_D–73° (MeOH). The structure and relative stereochemistry was established as 3-iso-19,20-dehydro- β -yohimbine **16** from a complete analysis of the ^1H NMR spectra of the product and its 17-*O*-acetate. Diaxial couplings of 10 Hz confirmed that the H-15, 16, 17 *trans-trans* stereochemistry had been retained, whereas the small *ae* and *ee* couplings of 5 and 2.5 Hz to the C-14 methylene protons showed that H-3 was equatorial, establishing a 3-15 *trans* orientation. From the known absolute stereochemistry of C-7 in secologanin, this would correspond in **16** to a 3 β (*R*)-configuration, which was confirmed by a –ve Cotton effect at 280 nm in the CD spectrum⁶. As with the heteroyohimbine, exclusive generation of this stereochemistry can again be attributed to axial attack by the indole at a C-3/N-4 iminium ion in a chair-like intermediate **22** with equatorial C-15, 16 and 17 substituents to give a *cis*-quinolizidine **16A** (Scheme 2). As well as affording routes to several other 3 β (*R*) alkaloids, since it was a kinetic product, C-3 in **16** could be readily inverted to access the thermodynamically preferred *trans*-quinolizidine series with 3 α (*S*)-configuration⁷.

Thus catalytic hydrogenation of the 19,20-double bond in **16** with Pd/C occurred only from the top face to give a quantitative yield of pseudo- β -yohimbine **17**, m.p. 135–138°, [α]_D+68° (MeOH). Moffat oxidation of **17** gave the 17-ketone, m.p. 220–223°, which was reduced stereoselectively with sodium borohydride in isopropanol to only pseudoyohimbine **18**, m.p. 250–253°. Its NMR spectrum was similar to that of **17**, except for small couplings to H-17 in accord with inversion to an axial OH group. Subsequent heating in glacial acetic acid epimerized C-3 to the thermodynamically preferred yohimbine **19**, characterised by a broadened doublet for H-3 with a *trans*-diaxial coupling of 11 Hz in the NMR spectrum and a +ve Cotton effect at 280 nm in the CD spectrum⁶, and identified by comparison with an authentic sample. A similar epimerization of **17** afforded the 17 epimer- β -yohimbine which

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions : (i) β -Glucosidase/pH 7.0 aq. buffer, 37°, 4 d, (ii) tryptamine, NaCNBH₂/MeOH, 2 d, (iii) 10% aq. HCl/Me₂CO 1 : 1, Δ , 2 h, (iv) H₂/Pd/MeOH, 12 h, (v) DMSO/Ac₂O, 16 h, (vi) NaBH₄, ¹PrOH, 20 h, (vii) AcOH, Δ , 2 d

was also produced directly by hydrogenation of 16 with Adams' catalyst. In subsequent stereoselective transformations involving isomerization to an 18,19-alkene, the versatile 3-iso-19,20-dehydro- β -yohimbine was converted into *epiallo* 20 and hence *allo* isomers of yohimbine, and via a novel regioselective hydration of the alkene also into the 18 β -hydroxy base 21, an analog of deserpidine⁸.

Antirhine and derivatives¹⁰

When we investigated the use of baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) as a cheap substitute for commercial β -glucosidase from almonds, in pH 7.5 buffer at 25° the cyclohexene aldehyde 14 was again obtained from secologanin ethylene acetal. Interestingly however, at pH 6.4, the C-1 aldehyde in the aglucone 3 was selectively reduced to give a 60–80% yield of a lactol 24 [M⁺ 272.1254 (C₁₃H₂₀O₆)] which showed hydroxyl and unconjugated ester carbonyl IR bands at 3425 and 1735 cm⁻¹, the former

being lost on acetylation to a monoacetate. Under neutral conditions in methanol there was no UV chromophore, but on addition of alkali a peak appeared at 270 nm, attributable to an anion from a β -aldehyde-ester 25 formed by opening of the lactol ring; on brief treatment with trifluoroacetic acid water was eliminated to create a β -alkoxy- α,β -unsaturated ester chromophore with λ_{max} 237 nm, which gave no base shift. Final confirmation of structure and stereochemistry as a 9 : 1 *R/S* mixture of C-9 epimers came from analysis of the ¹H NMR spectra of 24 and its derivatives. In particular, H-2 had negligible coupling with H-7 and only small *ae/ee* couplings with the C-1 methylene protons, proving that it was equatorial and thus that the 2,7-*cis*-geometry of secologanin had been conserved. We had observed that a 2,7-*trans*-isomer can be formed on occasion, if an acidic pH were not maintained, reversible enolisation of the C-1 aldehyde in the ring-opened aglucone 3 resulted in appreciable epimerization of C-2 before reduction. Thus in this

case, the availability of both the hydrolytic and reductive enzymes of yeast had enabled the labile hydrogen and the chiral centre at C-2 to be retained, in contrast to the above rearranged aglucones, a process difficult to achieve by any other means.

As a consequence of this retention of stereochemical integrity, it was evident to us that **24** might well be useful for synthesis of indole alkaloids related to antirrhine **32**, where difficulties arise in control of the stereochemistry at the chiral centres, particularly at C-20, the position corresponding to C-2 in the lactol. The alkaloid glabratine is a 9- β -D-glucosyloxy derivative of the as yet unknown 16-methoxycarbonyl-16,17-dehydro-antirrhine **28**⁹. We envisaged that it might be possible to prepare the parent structure **28** in one step from lactol **24** and tryptamine, and likewise serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine) should afford the 10-hydroxy derivative **29**, both of which we anticipated as likely to be natural products.

Thus, tryptamine and the lactol were heated in pH 3.5 aq. acetone buffer for three hours to afford two amorphous products, both of which had molecular ions at m/z 352 analysing for $C_{21}H_{24}N_2O_3$, and UV spectra constituting the sum of indolic and β -aminoacrylate chromophores (λ_{max} 222, 290 nm). The minor product had corresponding IR bands at ν_{max} 3327, 1666 and 1611 cm^{-1} , and was distinguished by a large peak in the mass spectrum at m/z 130 characteristic of an uncyclized tryptamine derivative. This was confirmed by the presence of an indolic α -proton at δ 7.0 in the NMR spectrum, which showed clearly that while the acetal had been cleaved, Pictet-Spengler cyclization had not taken place. Both H-3 at δ 4.53 and H-15 at 2.89 appeared as broadened singlets with only small 3J couplings to adjacent protons and a significant mutual $^4J_{W}$ -coupling of 1.5 Hz, which were consistent with the bridged amino-ether structure **26**.

With the major product the cyclization had been achieved, since there was no signal for any indolic α -proton in its NMR spectrum, which also confirmed the structure and stereochemistry as 16-methoxycarbonyl-16,17-dehydro-antirrhine **28**. A broad doublet at δ 4.90 assigned to H-3 had a large *trans-aa* coupling of 12 Hz to H-14_{ax} (δ 1.82), and this in turn had an *ae* coupling of 4 Hz to H-15 (δ 3.26) which must thus be equatorial. Hence the Pictet-Spengler reaction had occurred with complete stereoselectivity to give the 3,15-*trans*-product in a *trans*-quinolizidine conformation **28B** with an axial C-15 substituent (Scheme 3). A chair-like iminium intermediate would presumably have this substituent equatorial and the indole would add axially to afford an initial *cis*-quinolizidine **28A**, which then flips to the

observed *trans*-conformation. Formation of the minor product **26** must involve trapping of the intermediate by competitive addition of the C-21 alcohol to the iminium ion, a process likely to be reversible, and on heating under the same conditions as above it was indeed converted into **28**. As anticipated, serotonin afforded a similar pair of 10-hydroxy derivatives **27** and **29**¹⁰.

Antirrhine itself is one of the alkaloids with a C₉ rather than a C₁₀ unit, having lost the methoxycarbonyl group of secologanin during its biosynthesis. In an equivalent process, heating the lactol with alkali brought about deformylation as well as saponification, and the lactone **30** was obtained on acidifying. Prolonged treatment of **30** with tryptamine then afforded an amide **31**. Subsequent reduction to an amine with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of the acetal and concomitant Pictet-Spengler condensation gave antirrhine **32**, m.p. 106–108°, in 69% yield from lactol **24**. As in the previous case, generation of a single isomer must be due to similar stereoelectronic control, but it was interesting to note that in the NMR spectrum H-3 was a broad singlet at δ 4.2, indicating that it was equatorial and that antirrhine preferred a *cis*-quinolizidine conformation^{4c}.

Aspidosperma alkaloid analogs¹¹

Unlike the *Corynanthe* alkaloids, both enantiomeric series of *Aspidosperma* alkaloids occur in nature, even though derived from the same universal precursor, strictosidine. This dichotomy was plausibly attributed to the intervention of an achiral intermediate secodine with cyclization to one enantiomer or the other controlled by the chiral environment of an enzyme specific to the individual plant. Kuehne and co-workers¹² substantiated the proposed pathway by elegant *in vitro* syntheses of a transient secodine with biomimetic cyclization in high yield to vincadifformine. In the stereoselective syntheses of *Corynanthe* alkaloids from secologanin described above, the asymmetric centre at C-7 played a key role in inducing chirality at other centres. Hence we considered that the C-7 centre might also direct stereoselectivity in cyclization of secodine-like intermediates formed, by analogy with Kuehne's work, from an indoloazepine and an aldehyde derived from secologanin, and thus generate a novel series of chiral *Aspidosperma* alkaloid analogs.

Acetylation and catalytic hydrogenation of secologanin **5** afforded tetrahydrosecologanin tetra-acetate **33**, which was converted with thionyl chloride into the 5-chloro derivative, m.p. 125°. Zemplen deacetylation and hydrolysis with β -glucosidase in pH 5.0 aq. buffer then gave in 42% overall yield

Scheme 3. Reagents and conditions (i) Baker's yeast/pH 6.4 aq. buffer, 25°, 7 d, (ii) tryptamine or 5-hydroxytryptamine/Me₂CO/pH 3.5 aq. buffer, Δ, 3-5 h, (iii) Me₂CO/pH 3.5 aq. buffer, Δ, 5 h, (iv) 4 M aq. NaOH, Δ, 2 h then HCl, (v) tryptamine, EtOH, Δ, 5 d (vi) LiAlH₄, THF, Δ, 24 h

the 5-chloroaglucone **34**. We then required an intramolecular displacement of the chlorine at C-5 by the C-9 enol in the ring-opened aglucone **35** to obtain the C-1 aldehyde **38**, but there were competing reactions, viz. an alternative intramolecular cyclization of the hemiacetal to give **36**, or intermolecular hydrolysis leading to dihydrosweroside aglucone **37**. After some experimentation, it was found that standing in aq. acetone at pH 7.0 and 37° for three days achieved the desired conversion of **34** to give in 80% yield the aldehyde **38**, characterised *inter alia* by the lack of a shift of the UV maximum at 237 nm with alkali.

The indoloazepine **39**¹² and aldehyde **38** were then heated under reflux in methanol for four days, and subsequent chromatography afforded two isomeric products, characterized as lactams A, m.p. 238–240°, [α]_D +150°, and B, m.p. 205–207°, [α]_D –131°, in ca. 10 and 20% unoptimised yield, respectively. For both the products, the UV absorption with λ_{max} 226, 296, 326 nm was no longer indolic but corre-

sponded to a combination of β-anilinoacrylate and β-alkoxyacrylamide chromophores, and both the mass spectra had fragmentation characteristic of an *Aspidosperma* type skeleton.

Lactam A was assigned structure **42** and relative stereochemistry from a complete analysis of the ¹H NMR spectrum with decoupling and nOe experiments, and the absolute configuration of the spiro centre in lactam **42** was established as *S* and C-1 as *R* from correlation of the +ve optical rotation and, more specifically, the associated +ve Cotton effect at 326 nm in the CD spectrum with those of known alkaloids of the vincadifformine group¹³. For lactam B structure **43** was deduced in a similar way from ¹H NMR, nOe and CD spectra, a –ve Cotton effect establishing spiro *R* and C-1 *S* chirality. Since on heating lactam **42** in methanol it was slowly converted into **43**, but the latter gave no indication of reverting to **42** under the same conditions, lactam **42** must be the kinetic and **43** the thermodynamic

Scheme 4. Reagents and conditions (i) $\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{py}$, 12 h, (ii) $\text{H}_2/\text{Pd}/\text{EtOAc}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2 d, (iii) SOCl_2/DCM , 15 min, (iv) NaOMe , MeOH , 1.5 h, (v) β -glucosidase, pH 5 aq buffer, 37° , 2 d, (vi) pH 7.0 aq Me_2CO , 37° , 3 d, (vii) MeOH , Δ , 2-4 d, (viii) CHCl_3 , 7 d, (ix) MeOH , Δ , 6 d

products. Molecular modelling indicated that the difference in stability could be attributed essentially to an eclipsing interaction along the 2-7 bond in **42** that was relieved on conversion to **43**.

In a subsequent experiment the intermediate enamine **40** was isolated, the structure being established from the ^1H NMR spectrum with signals for both indoloazepine and monoterpene moieties, and characterized in particular by a singlet for the enamine H-1 at δ 6.81. Furthermore, nOe

studies not only showed that the major enamine had *E*-1,2-geometry, but also that it was the *E*-N,1-rotamer: irradiation of H-1 enhanced H-7 (4.5%), 9 (2.6%) and 2a' (9.7%) but not any protons of the ethyl group, whereas irradiation of H_a-3 gave enhanced peaks for protons on C-7' (5.2%) but not C-2'. Significantly, on standing in chloroform for seven days the enamine **40** was quantitatively converted into a single product, the kinetic lactam **42**. These results can be rationalized by invoking a secodine-type intermediate **41**

formed by retro-Michael fragmentation and lactamization of **8**, after *E/Z*-isomerisation of the enamine. At room temperature, cyclization is then directed by the C-7 chiral centre to the less hindered face of the enamide ring to afford the kinetic lactam **42** exclusively. However, at 65° reversal to **41** must occur and thus permit a slow accumulation of the thermodynamic lactam **43** by attack from the more hindered face, a process that is apparently irreversible under these conditions.

Thus using a secologanin derivative as a single chiral precursor, the synthesis had been achieved of two diastereomeric *Aspidosperma* alkaloid analogs. They are antipodal at every centre except one, the original C-7 centre, and if this were eliminated then we would have the prospect of readily controlled selective syntheses for both enantiomeric series. A further possibility is to use secologanin itself with the indoloazepine and hence develop routes to novel hybrid *Aspidosperma-Corynanthé* structures, combining various aspects of all the transformations described above. Again, it is evident that a wide variety of tryptamines and phenethylamines could also be used with the secologanin aglucones to generate a range of semisynthetic alkaloid analogs of pharmaceutical interest.

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